

Data Availability

This research is systematic literature review based on these articles:

1. Årsheim, H. (2018). Including and Excluding Indigenous Religion through Law. *Numen*, 65(5–6), 531–561. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15685276-12341511>
2. Gomez, A. R. (2024). Religion Scholarship on Indigenous Lands: Research, Relationship, and the Potential of Engaged Scholarship. *Journal for the Study of Religion, Nature and Culture*, 18(4), 484–501. <https://doi.org/10.1558/jsrnc.25258>
3. Hammons, C. S. (2016). Indigenous Religion, Christianity and the State: Mobility and Nomadic Metaphysics in Siberut, Western Indonesia. *The Asia Pacific Journal of Anthropology*, 17(5), 399–418. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14442213.2016.1208676>
4. Keegan, B. (2022). Contemporary Native American and Indigenous Religions: State of the field. *Religion Compass*, 16(9). <https://doi.org/10.1111/rec3.12448>
5. Maarif, S. (2023). Human (Relational) Dignity: Perspectives of Followers of Indigenous Religions of Indonesia. *Religions*, 14(7), 848. <https://doi.org/10.3390/re114070848>
6. Maćkowiak, A. M. (2024). Christian and Indigenous: Multiple “Religions” in Contemporary Toraja Funerals. *Religions*, 15(9), 1112. <https://doi.org/10.3390/re115091112>
7. Mendoza, R. J. (2024). Undisciplining the Museum: Indigenous Relationality as Religion. *Religions*, 15(11), 1325. <https://doi.org/10.3390/re115111325>
8. Najib, K. (2020). Government Ecology and the Indigenous Religion of the Suku Anak Dalam: Intersubjective Relations in Forest Conservation in Jambi, Indonesia. *Jurnal Manajemen Hutan Tropika (Journal of Tropical Forest Management)*, 26(3), 303–315. <https://doi.org/10.7226/jtfm.26.3.303>
9. Weatherdon, M. S. (2022). Religion, Animals, and Indigenous Traditions. *Religions*, 13(7), 654. <https://doi.org/10.3390/re113070654>
10. Weatherdon, M. (2022). Movement and Indigenous Religions: A Reconsideration of Mobile Ways of Knowing and Being. *Material Religion*, 18(1), 3–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17432200.2021.2015921>
11. Petri, D. P., & Klocek, J. (2025). External and Internal Threats to the Freedom of Religion or Belief of Indigenous Peoples in Latin America. *Religions*, 16(2), 209. <https://doi.org/10.3390/re116020209>
12. Tsing, A. (2023). A Multispecies Ontological Turn? In *The Routledge International Handbook of More-than-Human Studies* (pp. 116–128). Routledge.
13. Weaver, C. B. (2024). How Not to Undiscipline Religion and Science: Indigenous Ecological Knowledge, Epistemic Resistance, and the Settler Imagination. *Religions*, 15(11), 1290. <https://doi.org/10.3390/re115111290>
14. Zaluchu, S. E. (2025). Pray to the ancestors: a case study of Christianity and Nias indigenous religion. *Cogent Arts & Humanities*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311983.2025.2492419>